

INDUSTRY, AGRICULTURE, AND DOMESTIC WATERS OF KOROVULBOZOR DISTRICT

Research advisor:

b.f.n.prof. A.E. Xolliyev.

Bukhara State University Department of Geography

2nd year graduate student

Mirzayeva Muxlisa Elmurodovna

ABSTRACT: This article deals with the industry, agriculture, and internal waters of the Korovulbazar district.

Keywords: *grain and oil independence, oil and gas fields, forestry, irrigated areas, private horticulture.*

Our country straightened up and took a bold step to take a worthy place among the developed countries. The independence of grain and oil are the two main directions that make up the content and essence of the country's economy.

Setalontepa, Saritosh, Qarovulbozor, Gajdi, and other structures were found as a result of geological imaging, structures, and drilling works carried out in different years in the territory of Western Uzbekistan.

In 1953, as a result of the drilling operations carried out by the "Sredazneftterazvedka" trust in the Setalontepa field, a gas fountain erupted in the lower chalk layers. Therefore, by the decision of the government of the Republic, at the end of 1954, the base was located at the Qarovulbazar station. Saritosh Neftrazvedka" was established.

According to the decision of July 26, 1957, the construction of the first gas pipeline in Central Asia, Jarqok-Bukhara-Samarkand-Tashkent, began.

The opening of Saritosh - Qorovulbazar and Jargoq deposits laid the

foundation for the oil and gas region in Western Uzbekistan and accelerated oil and gas exploration in this region.

In 1963, the eruption of a powerful gas fountain from the 1st well in the Ortabuloq field once again confirmed that the land of Western Uzbekistan is rich in oil and gas deposits and became the basis for the further development of geological exploration.

The expedition team opened the Ortabulok and Dengizkol gas fields and calculated their reserves. Due to the high content of sulfur in the gas in these fields, the Mubarak gas processing plant was built and put into operation near the city of Mubarak. Today, this plant separates sulfur from gas, which is very necessary for our industry, most easily and cheaply.

On August 22, 1997, a "celebratory event" took place, i.e., the Bukhara Oil Refinery, named "Miracle of Uzbekistan", was put into operation. Large firms and banking companies from France, the USA, and Turkey participated in the construction of the plant (4 years). The factory was built on an area of 300 hectares, 7 km west of the center of the city of Qarovulbazar. "Neftchi" forestry was established. Near the city of Qarovulbazar, a town of oil workers rose.

During the construction of the plant, especially on the eve of its completion, 1,300 Turkish specialists were engaged in the installation, adjustment, and testing of equipment.

The countries of Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Iran, Turkey, and even Russia informed us about their requirements for the products of our factory.

Our country, which only yesterday bought oil products from abroad for foreign currency, now not only provides itself but also released it to the world market for sale.

Today, many high-quality A-76 and A-93 automobiles can accept gasoline. Fire extinguishers are automated.

Oil products are fed through pipelines to 24 gas stations at the same time.

The oil refinery is the only enterprise in the Commonwealth of Nations equipped with advanced equipment and technologies. A-№ 93, No.-76 gasoline, aviation kerosene, diesel fuel, fuel for steam boilers, liquefied gas, and sulfur make up the main part of the finished product.

Today, products produced in Qarovulbazar have reached all regions of our country. Interest in factory products is growing in foreign countries as well. Contracts have been signed with Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Iran, Turkey, and the products are being exported to Russia.

Development of protected lands began in the late 1970s, and 17,000 hectares of land have been opened so far. Agriculture plays an important role in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The government of the republic pays great attention to the reform of agriculture. It has a deep meaning. President of Uzbekistan I. Karimov in his speech on the topic "Abundant source of life in the development of agriculture" said that agriculture produces a net part of the new domestic product. The social structure of food production has changed radically.

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Inland waters

The district's water demand is provided by the Amu-Bukhara Canal, which was launched in the 1980s. Thanks to this channel, a large area of protected land was developed in the district and a new oasis of Qarovulbazar was created.

Currently, the irrigated areas are more than 16,000 hectares. A system of ditches and sewers has been created to eliminate ditches and sewage in the oasis

area. Due to the accumulation of Zovur waters, lakes such as Devkhana and Khadicha were formed in the northwestern part of the district.

The bare earth surface here is an opportunity for the creative power of the winds. In the years when the weather is favorable, the desert region is abundant with various food crops.

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The cisterns are silent witnesses of the long past, culture, and life of our people on the sides of the roads passing through deserts and steppes.

But time has destroyed many of these structures, which were built very firmly. Now they are few and far between in our country. Today, they are shining before our eyes and turning into ruins. The friendship channel starts after the Saritosh plateau. Dostlik Channel was built in 1981 by Abdullah Vahidov.

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The width of the canal is 17-18 m: the water tank is 24 m³ and is designed to irrigate 24 thousand hectares. However, there are 16,000 hectares of irrigated land in the Qarovulbazar district, and 1m³ of water is available for every 1,000 hectares of land.

There are 3 big bridges on the Friendship Canal. 2 concrete bridges and 1 iron bridge. After the third bridge, the canal divides its water in four directions at a place called Chetvyork.